

F.14 TOPST

Frequently Asked Questions

Updated: Oct 13, 2022

For general FAQs related to ROSES-2022 go [HERE](#)

Q1: What is TOPST?

A: TOPST stands for “Transform to Open Science Training.” The F.14 TOPST solicitation can be found [here](#). TOPST element solicits proposals for; (1) the development of the [ScienceCore](#), a discipline specific scientific use cases curriculum, (2) implementation of Summer Schools to teach OpenCore, and (3) implementation of Virtual Cohorts to complete OpenCore. The training material as well as the design of the learning activities should be targeted to audiences from undergraduate students to established scientists and managers from all science disciplines supported by NASA’s Science Mission Directorate (SMD).

Q2: What is the difference between OpenCore and ScienceCore?

A: TOPS has set itself the goal of meeting everyone where they are at in their open science journey. The core open science curriculum, or OpenCore, is currently being developed and will be available by April 1, 2023. OpenCore will introduce open science principles and practices to those who have not yet engaged deeply with open science. More details about OpenCore can be found [here](#). In contrast, the ScienceCore focuses on how open science can be used to generate new hypotheses and how to apply open science to particular disciplines. Areas of focus for the ScienceCore include how to access and analyze NASA science data including cloud-based data; open-source data, analysis, and visualization libraries both general and discipline-specific libraries; and creation, management, and sharing of reproducible science workflows and results. ScienceCore components may extend OpenCore concepts or cover SMD foundational discipline-specific themes leveraging, where possible, existing NASA cloud-based datasets. Both OpenCore and ScienceCore final products will be permissively licensed and contributed to the [TOPS GitHub](#).

Q3: What are “summer schools” and “virtual cohorts”? Why are they different?

A: Summer Schools are meetings that are designed to train NASA’s SMD science teams in Open Science and to increase opportunities for participation in science team activities by a diverse community. The TOPS open science curriculum, [OpenCore](#), will be taught during summer school. Since there are 5 OpenCore modules, each 2.5 hours, that must be taught, it may be a week-long meeting, with a module taught each morning and science team activities in the afternoon. Virtual Cohorts consist of individuals who are taking the OpenCore asynchronous online, but are seeking a community with which to discuss the information as well as ask questions. Virtual Cohorts will help online learners find that community, encourage completion of the online course, and help facilitate learning. Although Summer Schools can also be held virtually, they differ from Virtual Cohorts in that Summer Schools are taught by an instructor (or several instructors) in a “classroom” setting, in five sequential days. Virtual Cohorts are primarily self-paced, with group enrichment and discussion held periodically.

Q4: Are there any requirements for the selection of summer school locations?

A: Priority will be placed on proposals that hold activities at or heavily involve non-R1 Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCU), Hispanic Serving Institutions (HSI) and Tribal Colleges and Universities (TCU) or have previously held similar activities that have documented participation and sustained engagement by underrepresented communities.

Q5: What review process will be used to evaluate the TOPST proposals?

A: Dual-anonymous peer review process: not only are proposers unaware of the identity of the members on the review panel, but the reviewers do not have explicit knowledge of the proposal teams during the scientific evaluation of the proposal. More information is available [here](#).

Q6: Should proposals include an Open-Source Science Development Plan or an Equal Access Plan?

A: All proposals must submit an Open-Source Science Development Plan that describes how project materials will be openly available. Summer Schools and Virtual Cohorts proposals must also submit an Equal Access Plan. The Open-Source Science

Development Plan must conform to [Earth Science Division guidelines](#). Please see the F.14 solicitation for more details. The Equal Access Plans are described in F.14 Section 4.2.1. Here we provide some useful references:

- NASA's Mission Equity initiative: <https://www.nasa.gov/mission-equity>
- Accessibility requirements for information and communication technology: <https://www.access-board.gov/ict/>
- Universal Design and Accessibility: <https://www.section508.gov/develop/universal-design/>

Q7: Open-Source Science Development plans are usually not included within the S/T/M page limit. Does that also apply to the Equity Access Plan?

A: Neither the Open-Source Science Development plan nor the Equity Access Plan are counted in the S/T/M page limit. In addition to the 10 pages per topic for the S/T/M section, one additional page is allotted for the Proposal Summary, two additional pages are allotted for the anonymized Open-Source Science Development Plan (see Section 4.1), and, for Summer Schools and Virtual Cohorts proposals only, two additional pages are allocated for the anonymized Equal Access Plan (see Section 4.2.1).

Q8: Who is eligible for TOPST?

A: See Section III in the ROSES-2022 Summary of Solicitations [HERE](#).

Q9: Can non-U.S. institutions submit proposals?

A: Proposals from non-U.S. institutions are welcome, but they must be on a no-exchange-of-funds basis. Funding may not be requested to support activities at non-US institutions but may be requested to support activities at US institutions, e.g., for funding a Co-Investigator at a U.S. institution. In other words, non-U.S. institutions may submit the proposal as a lead organization but can not request or receive any funds directly to them; it can be used to support US institutions or partners.

Q10: Does a PI have to be a US citizen? Are green card holders eligible?

A: The institution receives the award and funding must only go to an US institution. The Principal Investigator (PI) does not need to be a US citizen, but must be legally permitted to work in the US to receive funding.

Q11: Can a for-profit apply (and be the lead) for this grant?

A: Yes, a for-profit can be the lead for a proposal to this solicitation. Please see the [NASA Guidebook for Proposers](#) for further details.

Q12: Is it possible to submit more than one proposal?

A: Each proposal is limited to a single topic, but any organization or PI may submit multiple proposals.

Q13: If an organization submits more than one proposal, does it need to be for different elements of the call? Or can we have more than one proposal for the same element (for example, more than one proposal for ScienceCore, Summer Schools, or Virtual Cohorts)?

A: You can submit multiple proposals for the same element.

Q14: How frequently will this be solicited?

A: This is the first time a solicitation of this scope has been released. At this time, we do not plan to solicit this as part of ROSES23, and the frequency of the solicitation will be determined only after review of this solicitation.

Q15: How many awards will be given for each type of proposal?

A: The number of proposals selected will be dependent on the number and quality of proposals submitted and on the availability of funds.

	ScienceCore Curriculum	Summer Schools	Virtual Cohorts
Total Budget	**\$1.3 million per year	**\$1.2 million per year	**\$400,000 per year
Duration	Max 2 years	Max 3 years	Max 3 years
# of Projects	6-12	3-4	2-3

**** Total budget divided across projects**

Q16: What would be an appropriate project start date?

A: A start date beginning sometime between May and June 2023 would be reasonable. Selection letters will be available ~mid-Feb. Projects might start earlier at their own risk of funds not being available. On average, it takes 3-6 months for funds to be available after selection letters. See Table below.

Q17: Is there any restriction on the number of Co-Investigators?

A: There are no restrictions on the number of co-investigators.

Q18: Are there restrictions/benefits to including undergraduate student involvement for academic institutions?

A: There are no restrictions on inclusion of undergraduate students, and you can consider the inclusion aspect of their involvement.

Q19: Normally Collaborators are unfunded and Co-Investigators are funded. Is that not the case here?

A: As stated on p. 34 of the [NASA Guidebook for Proposers](#), a Co-Investigator may or may not receive funding through the award. And, p. 35 states that a Collaborator is unfunded.

Q20: Is there any template for this solicitation?

A: This is the first time a solicitation of this scope has been released, so we do not yet have a template for this solicitation. For more information about templates for ROSES, please see the [ROSES FAQs](#).

Q21: What will the expected clearance process be for any materials and code developed? Will it need to go through NASA's software clearance?

A: Material developed as part of a selected proposal should go through the release process, if one exists, for your institution and be described in the Open Source Science plan. While restricted material such as export control may be described, the developed material should not contain any restricted information.